

Cogwheel workshops: antimicrobial resistance, infectious (animal and human) and foodborne diseases surveillance and prevention

OHEJP cogwheel workshops are designed to foster collaborations, and to develop joint resources."

Sharing knowledge and translating our science to policy are at the forefront of the One Health European Joint Programme's (OHEJP) focus. Our research projects aim to address gaps in scientific knowledge in the foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats domains. By sharing our knowledge and developing joint resources with other European Union (EU) funded initiatives and projects we can consolidate our efforts to help understand and develop approaches for One Health issues.

The OHEJP Work Package 4 was specifically set up to foster collaborations and, working with OHEJP Project Leaders' of Joint Research Projects and Joint Integrative Projects, identify synergies, joint priorities and opportunities to develop joint resources.

Eight Cogwheel Workshops focused on antimicrobial resistance, infectious (animal and human) and foodborne diseases surveillance and prevention were organised to fulfil these identified aims.

The **first workshop** was organised with the participation of **COMPARE**, an EU funded project working on the use of new genome technology to help speeding up the detection of and response to humans' and animals' disease outbreaks worldwide. Data analysis pipelines, standard operating procedures (for bioinformatics and lab-based work) and harmonised data standards were discussed during this workshop. Given the common research interests between COMPARE and the OHEJP projects IMPART, LISTADAPT, ORION and METASTAVA, concrete points of collaboration and opportunities to redirect activities were identified. Appropriate formal agreements need to be in place.

The **second workshop** highlighted the **EFFORT** (Ecology from Farm to Fork Of microbial drug Resistance and Transmission) project that studies the ecology of antimicrobial resistance and the complex interactions between commensal and pathogenic microbial communities in animals, the food chain and the environment. For this purpose, the EFFORT project uses metagenomics, modelling methodology and systematic integration of data which are of great interest for the OHEJP consortium.

Follow Us!

@OneHealthEJP

ONE Health EJP

#OneHealthEJP #OneHealth #StrongerTogether

Synergies and opportunities for collaboration (such as methods and data sharing) were especially identified between EFFORT and the OHEJP projects [ARDIG](#), [ORION](#) and [RaDAR](#). Appropriate formal agreements need to be in place in order to facilitate cooperation.

The targets for the *third workshop* activity were the projects INNUENDO, IRIDA and COMPARE. [INNUENDO](#) designed an analytical platform and standard procedures for the use of whole-genome sequencing for foodborne pathogens surveillance and outbreaks' investigation. The [IRIDA](#) (The Integrated Rapid Infectious Disease Analysis) project, a Canadian-led initiative, provides an open source, end-to-end platform for public health genomics and studies the emergence and transmission of antimicrobial resistance genes from farm-to-fork. [COMPARE](#) aims to develop an analytical framework and information sharing platform that will enable identification, containment and mitigation of emerging infectious diseases and foodborne outbreaks. The [INNUENDO](#), [IRIDA](#) and [COMPARE](#) projects have several bioinformatic activities that are relevant for the OHEJP projects. It is necessary to clarify how synergies between the projects can be best exploited, and how methods, and data can be shared between the projects. To further encourage bioinformaticians and epidemiologists from veterinary, public health and food sectors to work together and produce workable, programmable definitions of clustering, an online Thematic integrative meeting entitled "practical use of NGS" was held on the 29th April 2020.

The target for the *fourth workshop* was the [InfAct](#) (Information for Action) project. InfAct involves 40 partners and 28 countries and aims to strengthen national and EU health information systems. For that, they are focusing on:

- Establishing a sustainable research infrastructure to support population health and health | system performance assessment;
- Strengthening European health information and knowledge bases, as well as health information research capacities to reduce health information inequalities;
- Supporting health information interoperability and innovative health information tools and data sources.

No major overlaps between InfAct and the OHEJP projects represented were identified. The OHEJP Science to Policy translation can, however, gain further inspiration from the InfAct's strategy example for interaction with the national policy and decision makers. The InfAct 's Assembly of Members focus more on national partners with whom have strong contacts, rather than international ones like ECDC.

The target for the *fifth workshop* was five projects funded through the 9th call from the Joint Programming Initiative on Antimicrobial Resistance ([JPIAMR](#)) on Diagnostics and Surveillance:

- [MAGITICS](#): MACHine learning for diGital diagnostICS of antimicrobial resistance;
- [K-STaR](#): A K-mer Based Approach for Institutional AMR Surveillance, Transmission Monitoring, and Rapid Diagnostics;
- [OASIS](#): One Health AMR Surveillance through Innovative Sampling;
- [TRiuMPH](#): Improving the TRicycle protocol: upscaling to national Monitoring, detection of CPE and WGS pipelines for One Health Surveillance;
- [IDx](#): An exploration of regulatory, corporate, relational, and technical barriers to uptake of diagnostics in the fight against AMR.

Aspects of the JPIAMR projects covering economy and their approaches to omics demonstrated relevance to OHEJP projects. In November 2020, the JPIAMR organised a workshop on AMR surveillance, to which the OHEJP was invited in order to strengthen collaboration.

The target for the *sixth workshop* was the [SafeConsume](#) project. The SafeConsume consortium consists of 32 partners from 14 countries in Europe and the overall objective of the project is to reduce health burden from foodborne illness through changing consumer behaviour. The SafeConsume project

Follow Us!

@OneHealthEJP

ONE Health EJP

#OneHealthEJP #OneHealth #StrongerTogether

aims to provide effective, science-based and sustainable strategies for food authorities, market actors and the research community to help consumers mitigate risk, and therefore reduce the health burden from food-borne illness in Europe. Their project structure and the way they measure impact is inspiring for the OHEJP consortium. The OHEJP project [TOXOSOURCES](#) has been successfully collaborating with SafeConsume (DISH collaboration) and following the workshop discussion on further collaborations with OHEJP projects' [OH-HARMONY-CAP](#) and [IMPART](#) are underway to make Europe equally efficient in foodborne diseases detection. This was the first workshop to include the PhD students and demonstrated its suitability as a platform for early career researchers to be involved in scientific discussion training.

Throughout the five year Programme the One Health EJP has continued to build European networks and engage a wider global audience, and has been proactive in encouraging a collaborative approach to scientific research. ”

The target for the *seventh workshop* was the [VEO](#) project. The vision of VEO is to establish a Versatile forecasting, nowcasting, and tracking system (VEO) serving as an interactive observatory for the generation and distribution of high-quality actionable information for evidence-based early warning, risk assessment and monitoring of Emerging Infectious Diseases and Antimicrobial resistance by public health actors and researchers in the One-Health domain. Later in the workshop planning process, the [MOOD](#) project was also suggested as a relevant project to include in the cogwheel workshop, as MOOD and VEO had common deliverables. The MOOD project aims to harness state-of-the-art big data mining and analysis techniques to improve detection, monitoring and assessment of infectious disease (re-)emergence in Europe. The VEO and MOOD projects covered topics highly relevant for the OHEJP within their project scope. The OHEJP has already confronted the issues surrounding the sharing of raw data regarding microbiomes from poultry. It is important to follow the [Nagoya protocol](#) (international agreement aiming at sharing the benefits arising from the utilisation of genetic resources in a fair and equitable way) that has a material transfer agreement. It was commented that it can already be challenging to share research material only within one country, and thus even more challenging within projects with international partners. The platform MOOD will be available to public health and veterinary health institutes.

The target for the *eight workshop* was [ELIXIR](#). ELIXIR is an intergovernmental organisation that brings together life science resources in Europe, to coordinate the available resources into a single infrastructure and therefore simplify finding and sharing data, exchanging expertise and agreeing on best practices. Fruitful discussions around data sharing (including “sensitive” data) between institutions within and between countries, legal issues and GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation), databases and infrastructure for data storage and management, and training on the best software, tools and workflows took place during the workshop. As handling data in accordance with the law and principles of [FAIR](#) are resource demanding, it was suggested that OHEJP Work Package 4 should create the context for involvement in ELIXIR and in further collaboration initiatives with ELIXIR. ELIXIR was identified as a suitable contributor to the [OHEJP Simulation Exercise](#) as it could provide resources to identify, trace and predict future outbreaks (novel pathogens or AMR). Some institutions and OHEJP projects also clearly stated specific action points to approach ELIXIR and look further into topics about storage and relevant tools.

Throughout the five year Programme the One Health EJP has continued to build European networks and engage a wider global audience, and has been proactive in encouraging a collaborative approach to scientific research. The cogwheel workshops are just part of the activities the OHEJP has initiated; we have made great progress in encouraging a more collaborative, integrative approach across Europe to come together to achieve the common goal of protecting global health.

One Health EJP has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 773830.

Follow Us!

@OneHealthEJP

ONE Health EJP

#OneHealthEJP #OneHealth #StrongerTogether